

A Study to Assess the Common Occupational Health Problems among Daily Wage Workers in Selected Areas of Rohtas, Bihar

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ABSTRACT

Background: Daily wage workers in the unorganized sector are highly vulnerable to occupational health hazards due to poor working conditions, lack of protective equipment, and limited access to healthcare services. **Objective:** To assess common occupational health problems among daily wage workers and determine their association with selected variables. **Methods:** A quantitative descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 daily wage workers in selected areas of Rohtas, Bihar. Convenience sampling technique was used. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and checklist. Analysis was done using frequency, percentage, and chi-square test. **Results:** Majority (72%) of workers reported at least one occupational health problem. Musculoskeletal disorders (58%) were most common, followed by respiratory problems (32%), skin diseases (27%), and injuries (21%). Significant association was found between working hours, use of protective equipment, and health problems ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Occupational health problems are highly prevalent among daily wage workers. Preventive strategies such as health education and safety measures are essential.

Keywords: Occupational health, daily wage workers, hazards, Bihar

INTRODUCTION

Occupational health focuses on the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental, and social well-being of workers. In India, a large proportion of the workforce is employed in the unorganized sector, where occupational safety measures are often neglected. Daily wage workers are exposed to multiple hazards such as heavy physical work, dust, chemicals, noise, and unsafe environments. These exposures lead to various health problems including musculoskeletal disorders, respiratory illnesses, skin diseases, and injuries. Despite the high burden, occupational health problems among daily wage workers remain underreported, especially in rural areas like Rohtas, Bihar. Hence, this study was undertaken to assess the common occupational health problems and associated factors.

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METHODOLOGY

Component	Description
Research Approach	Quantitative
Research Design	Descriptive cross-sectional
Setting	Selected areas of Rohtas, Bihar
Population	Daily wage workers
Sample Size	100
Sampling Technique	Convenience sampling
Tool	Structured questionnaire & checklist
Data Collection	Interview method
Data Analysis	Frequency, percentage, chisquare

Inclusion Criteria:

Workers aged 18–60 years willing to participate

Ethical Considerations:

Informed consent was obtained and confidentiality maintained

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Workers by Demographic Characteristics (N=100)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age 18–30	30	30%
Age 31–45	45	45%
Age 46–60	25	25%
Male	70	70%
Female	30	30%

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Table 2: Prevalence of Occupational Health Problems

Health Problem	Frequency	Percentage
Musculoskeletal disorders	58	58%
Respiratory problems	32	32%
Skin diseases	27	27%
Injuries	21	21%

Table 3: Association Between Working Conditions and Health Problems

Variable	Health Problem Present	Health Problem Absent	Chisquare	p-value
Long working hours (>8 hrs)	50	10	6.25	<0.05
No protective equipment	55	15	7.10	<0.05

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that a majority of daily wage workers suffered from occupational health problems, with musculoskeletal disorders being the most common. This finding is consistent with previous studies indicating high physical strain among laborers. Respiratory and skin problems were also common due to exposure to dust and chemicals. The study further found a significant association between working conditions and health problems, highlighting the role of occupational risk factors. Lack of awareness and non-use of protective equipment contributed significantly to these issues.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

The study concludes that occupational health problems are highly prevalent among daily wage workers in Rohtas, Bihar. Musculoskeletal disorders, respiratory issues, and skin diseases are the most common problems.

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There is a strong need for:

- Health education programs
- Use of personal protective equipment
- Regular health check-ups
- Implementation of occupational safety policies

Improving working conditions can significantly enhance workers' health and productivity.

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